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Communicative Language Teaching

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***Abstract:** The 1st President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov`s speech at the International Conference named «Upbringing of Educated and Intellectually Advanced Generation as the Most Important Condition of Sustainable Development and Modernization of the Country» was held with participation of representatives of the international organizations. To start with, it needs stressing that the education reforms program adopted fifteen years ago and dubbed the National Program for Training of Specialists. It stands as an inseparable and integral part of our own «Uzbek model» of economic and political reforms based on gradual and evolutionary principle of building a new society in the country.*

The program, itself a product of an in-depth research and study, summary of the practice hoarded by advanced nations, aims to eliminate completely stereotypes and dogmas of the communist ideology imposed in the past, consolidation of democratic values in the minds of people, first and foremost among the growing generation. In a word, the program is directed at nurturing a comprehensively advanced individual with independent thinking and outlook, with its own preferences and firm civic position in life. It was simply impossible to further that goal without radical reconstruction and transformation of the education system that had been there for many years. From the definitions we would like to generalize and say that language is the mean of communication. Since there are a lot of countries in the world, there are many languages too. There are also world languages which are widely used by the people all over the world. They are Spanish, French, English, Arabian, Russian, Italian. I am not mistaken if I say that among these languages English is the most widely used one. Following facts will help us to prove our opinion:

More than a quarter of the world`s population uses English regularly. More than 500 million people can speak English reasonably well. “Reasonably well” can mean a lot of things. However we do know that there are 300 million native speakers of English. In addition, there are certainly far more than 200 million non-native speakers in the world who speak at least “reasonable” English.

The role of instructional materials is considered to be very important. It is said; “Practitioners of Communicative Language Teaching view materials as the way of influencing the quality of classroom

interaction and language use. Communicative Language Learning advocates have proposed certain interactive structures that are considered optimal for learning the appropriate rules and practices in conversing in a new language.

Key words: *social interaction, cognitive development, creativity, native speakers, communicative approach, classroom management skills, text-based materials, task-based materials, realia, real-life situations.*

Introduction

What state will be powerful, what people will be mighty in XXI century? It is possible to answer this question so: the state with the intellectual and comprehensively developed population, with knowing, proud, patriotic youth

Islam Karimov, the 1st Prezident of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The historical changes took place in Uzbekistan, since Independence and sovereignty have been obtained in September 1991, after that in Independent Uzbekistan many political, economical, cultural and social factors have altered. Therefore, from the very time of getting Independence, the first president of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov started to change Educational System and the attempts reflected on developments in Educational System in 1997, the Educational system and personnel Training so high developed before Independence no longer meets requirements of democratic and market changes occurred in the Republic today.

It should be noted that the national Program of Personnel training had some unique features. The reforms are carried out on an extensive scale and are supported scientifically “Education and upbringing is the result of consciousness. At the same time, they imply the level of development of consciousness, in other words, are the key factors that expand and enrich the national spirit. Spirit cannot be developed without changing the consciousness on the basis of change in the system of education and upbringing”- said our first President Islam Karimov. Certainly, we can see great changes in our educational system. One of them is increasing the role of English language and implementing contemporary methods in teaching foreign languages, etc. Education is considered to be precedence in the sphere of social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Nowadays in our Republic a great attention is being paid to broadcasting of the English language. Earlier English has been taught from the fifth grade in most secondary schools of Uzbekistan, whereas now a new decree was issued on 10 December 2012 concerning teaching of this language from the first grade of all secondary schools.

The highest objective of reformation in Uzbekistan is to revive those traditions, fill them with new content and set up all necessary conditions achieving peace and democracy, prosperity, cultural advancement freedom of conscience and intellectual maturity for every person on earth.

According to the requirement of the National Program of Personnel training and reforming of highest education in the republic of Uzbekistan, it is important to make effective changes in the System of Higher Education.

As our first president highlighted “our young generation must be quick-cutter, wiser, healthier and, of course, must be happier than us”.

In order to achieve “harmoniously developed generation” Educators should use all the suitable aids.

A scientific approach to foreign language teaching has always been of a great attention in Uzbekistan and every student has always strived to learn a foreign language and acquire habits and skills in using it.

Teaching a foreign language is a hard work. But hard work nearly always brings success when a teacher does his best to make his pupils do their work.

P.Currey is right when he says that “few people realize what an increasing expenditure of thought and energy is essential for teaching this subject indeed, a foreign.”

When a person is in the process of becoming bilingual, social interaction is a factor that contributes in that language process. Brown cited long stating “Interaction and input are two major players in the process of acquisition”. Similarly, Ziglari cited Vygotsky to state that “Social interaction is primary in language acquisition...meaning is socially constructed and emerges out of the learner interactions with his/her environment. Learning occurs when biological mental functions evolve into higher functions through social interaction”. Therefore, I can say that social interaction develops higher mental processes through internalization of external surroundings. For instance, the human beings through interacting and working with each other built the communities and civilizations; because through social interaction I transmit ideas, thoughts, emotions, knowledge to other people. In that sense, learning a second language encourages cognitive development, creativity, and thinking in children; if children are more exposed to the foreign language in meaningful social surroundings, they will find more opportunities to learn because social environments encourage their mental processes; similarly, Vygotsky stated that social interaction plays a fundamental role in the process of cognitive development. All people in normal conditions have the mental capability to interact in a foreign language, but it is necessary to develop grammatical features, phonetic conventions, alphabet, and vocabulary. “People are naturally programmed for language and language develops in the same way that other biological functions develop,” they said. Even with the natural capacity to learn languages, children need interaction to master language development. In addition, the social interaction must be taken into account in the learning process of a foreign language in order to develop the competence to communicate. The ability to use a language for social purposes is printed very early in the acquisition experience of native speakers; at this point, if this social competence is introduced earlier in the foreign language process it will generate a correct communicative convention expressing and receiving messages that are meaningful between speakers.

Can we imagine our life without a language? The answer is, certainly, no. So, what is language itself?

People who have had a chance to consult the Concise Columbia Encyclopedia might have responded to this question with oversimplified “systematic communication by vocal symbols.” In “The Language Instinct,” a sophisticated statement might have come:

Language is a complex, specialized skill, which develops in the child spontaneously, without conscious effort or formal instruction, is deployed without awareness of its underlying logic, is qualitatively the same in every individual, and is distinct from more general abilities to process information or behave intelligently.¹

¹ Pinker., “The Language Instinct” New York,1994.-P 18

On the other hand, a standard definition out of introductory textbooks might be offered: “Language is a system of arbitrary conventionalized vocal, written, or gestural symbols that enable members of given community intelligibly with one another.”

The procedures of communicative language teaching often requires teachers to understand that it is not teacher-centered classroom management. Teachers need acquire less teacher-centered classroom management skills. They should organize the classroom as a setting to communication or communicative activities. During the activity teacher monitors and encourages the students, at the same time he notes the gaps in lexis, grammar, and strategy for later commentary. At the conclusion the teacher leads in the debriefing assisting the students in self-correction discussion.

The role of instructional materials is considered to be very important. It is said; “Practitioners of Communicative Language Teaching view materials as the way of influencing the quality of classroom interaction and language use. Materials thus have the primary role of promoting communicative language use.”² Materials which are currently used in Communicative Language Teaching is divided into three kinds. They are text-based, task-based, and realia.

Text-based materials. There are several textbooks which direct and support Communicative Language Teaching. Sometimes their content give grading and sequencing of language practice unlike structurally organized texts.

Task-based materials. To support Communicative Language Teaching classes different games, role plays, and task-based communication activities have been prepared. Realia. As many teachers brought into the classroom “from life” materials, language based realia, such as signs, magazines, advertisements, and newspapers, or graphic and visual sources like maps, pictures, symbols, graphs, and charts which can build around communicative activity were introduced to the class in teaching language.

Methods

The purposes of this research are to show how it is important to use CLT methods in teaching English and to identify the learners’ responses toward the use of different types of CLT approaches. Therefore, this research will be conducted to answer these questions:

1. Did you feel motivated doing the task? If yes, why?
2. Did you have a clear purpose for fulfilling the task?
3. Is the task close to real life? Could you imagine encountering such a situation in real life?
4. In what modes of interaction did you work (individual, group work, pair work)? Was the mode of interaction useful? Why?
5. How was the classroom arranged? (Rows of tables with chairs, circle, semicircle, etc.) What for?
6. Did the trainer recommend what kind of vocabulary or grammar structures to use or did you choose them yourself?
7. What was more important in this activity: what you said or how you said it?
8. Did the trainer correct your mistakes? What could a trainer do if he/she notices mistakes in your speech?

² Richards J, Rodgers Th., “Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching”. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000. -p168

The communicative approach could be said to be the product of educators and linguists who had grown dissatisfied with the audio-lingual and grammar-translation methods of foreign language instruction.

The origins of Communicative Language Teaching are to be found in the changes in the British languages teaching tradition dating from the late 1960s. Interest in and development of communicative-style teaching mushroomed in the 1970s; authentic language use and classroom exchanges where students engaged in real communication with one another became quite popular. The role of the instructor in CLT is quite different from traditional teaching methods. In the traditional classroom, the teacher is in charge and "controls" the learning. In CLT the teacher serves as more of a facilitator, allowing students to be in charge of their own learning.

The principles of the communicative approach

- real-life situations
- creative role-plays
- Simulations
- surveys
- projects
- spontaneity and improvisation
- ³Use of idiomatic/ everyday language
- Fresh and real materials
- Use of visual stimuli

The method we will examine in this chapter advises teachers to consider their students as 'whole persons.' Whole-person learning means that teachers consider not only their students' intellect, but also have some understanding of the relationship among students' feelings, physical reactions, instinctive protective reactions, and desire to learn. The Community Language Learning Method takes its principles from the more general Counseling-Learning approach developed by Charles A. Curran. Curran studied adult learning for many years. He was also influenced by Carl Rogers' humanistic psychology (Rogers 1951; Brown 1994), and he found that adults often feel threatened by a new learning situation. They are threatened by the change inherent in learning and by the fear that they will appear foolish. Curran believed that a way to deal with the fears of students is for teachers to become 'language counselors.' A language counselor does not mean someone trained in psychology; it means someone who is skillful at understanding struggling students' face as they attempt to internalize another language. The teacher who can 'understand' can indicate his acceptance of the student. By understanding students' fears and being sensitive to them, he can help students overcome their negative feelings and turn them into positive energy to further their learning.

Results

This chapter focuses on the analysis of collected data and obtained results after implementation of two data collecting methods – two forms of questionnaires and observation. More precisely, this chapter presents the analysis of the collected data and gives results on how using CLT methods at the lessons.

³ Richards J, Rodgers Th. "Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching". Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002. -P.216-217

It can help develop young learners` skills in Uzbekistan schools, the methods of applying these games at the lessons, the role of CLT games in teaching EFL, recommendations to teachers of English on applying CLT to the teaching process in Uzbekistan`s context, etc. The statistical results of the study were consistent with the aim of this study, which indicates effectiveness of using communicative approaches in teaching English, especially in developing speaking skills.

There is the result of using CLT methods during my lessons:

At the 1st lesson most students will be active listeners; at the 2nd lesson most students will be speakers; At the 3rd lesson most students will be pay attention to their grammar (they try to speak as fluently as it is possible); At the 4th lesson, during the project work, most students will be work fruitfully then previous lessons. It shows that if our students work together, they will achieve good results in learning English. Communicative approaches are the best approaches among new pedagogical methods.

The best games as the Communicative Language Teachings are: “Simon says”, “Crocodile”, “Guess”. I used these games by using Total physical response. My students learned new words more effectively than other games. “Simon says” was the best game among them. That’s why I tried to use it more than others.

(especially for primary school pupils.)

As for problems which may occur during games, 9 respondents (14 %) stated that they sometimes feel embarrassed to perform at the blackboard, when all the attention is on them but feel okay in whole class work. 7 pupils (11%) said that sometimes they misunderstand their classmates when they perform and that’s why they find it difficult to learn. 20 pupils (31%) stated that because of their classmates’ misbehavior they have difficulty concentrating on the lesson. The majority of pupils (28 pupils) (43 %) stated that they do not think there are minuses in these games. On the contrary, they are enjoyable.

Fifteen questionnaires were distributed to secondary school teachers Ferghana district. On their basis the following graphs were produced.

For example, in questionnaires you can meet following question:

1. Do you use communicative methods during the lesson?
2. Did you feel motivated doing the task? If yes, why?
3. Is it difficult for you to prepare deductive games for the lesson as far as the time matter is concerned?

It is not surprising that all the teachers responded that they use communicative methods during the English lessons, as they in general are very enjoyable. No doubt, all the teachers gave positive answers for other questions, too.

It is evident that a predominant number of the respondents (10) consider the preparation of deductive games to be sometimes highly time-consuming. Rather a few respondents (4) believe that the preparation of games is always time-consuming. Only 1 respondent replied that it is not complicated to prepare this type of games for the lesson.

Open-ended questions

This type of questionnaire is a qualitative data, which is expected to reveal the teachers' opinions about CLT as a pedagogical tool. Even though most of the questions that can seem too primitive and the answers to them can be found in different sources such as Internet or library, I decided that it is important to know the real beliefs and opinions of real people.

All the findings indicate that using mime games do impact young learners' spoken interactions and motivation positively. However, there are at least four considerations teachers need to pay attention to based on this study. Firstly, the classroom atmosphere has to guarantee the participation of all the students in the process of the lesson. Moreover, teachers should not only be able to create a positive 'emotional atmosphere', but to sustain it throughout the lesson. For this reason, observing students while following a class routine will help teachers to test students' willingness and attitudes, to both control misbehavior before it gets out of hand and increase their interest in the lesson.

Teachers should clearly identify the aspect of language they want the students to develop and select a suitable assessment model (Cameron, 2001). Teachers should be aware that explaining grammar rules to young learners or even secondary school pupils is useless and grammar structures can be taught in the context, in a natural way. Undoubtedly, one of the advantages of using communicative methods is to provide learners with the opportunity to use language out of the textbook context, while participating in real spoken interactions and facilitating the acquisition of English.

On the basis of my own teaching experience I can say without hesitation that communicative methods should be included generally in the school curricula as they develop communication skills and build confidence. Even though the research presents the positive aspects of using communicative methods in language teaching, teachers should have to be aware of drawbacks and disadvantages its usage may

bring. First of all, considerable disadvantage of activities is that they are usually not embedded in wider context, they are short 'extra activities', which are easily discarded if there is not sufficient time. Moreover, such kind of activities are usually artificial, difficult to monitor, can cause embarrassment, teachers' fear of losing control, spontaneity is lost, timing lessons is difficult, activities may not be suitable for all levels.

Discussion

Communicative language teaching is indispensable to school pupils. With the appropriate CLT materials, a conducive environment, and with teacher's adequate educational qualifications, good communicative approaches will help produce pupils who perform well in other subjects. Government, teachers, and parents have major roles to play in the education of pupils in primary schools, especially on English as a school subject. Eighty-eight percent of respondent felt that teachers play a greater role. Government is the major provider of education through funding, rules, and regulations. The attitudes of parents help motivate children. To promote CLT and eliminate the threat of communication disabilities among people, the following recommendations are made: Teachers must acknowledge the importance of communicative approaches and must plan an effective programme of CLT instruction with a focus on promoting English atmosphere among pupils in their schools. Parents should provide a stimulating English environment for their children and wards. They should encourage their children to communicate at home too. Books should be provided for them to improve their communicative and other skills. They should also encourage their children to watch children's educational television. This will go a long way in improving their phonetic and vocabulary development. They should cultivate the habit of using their leisure to read for pleasure. Government at the federal, state, and local levels should provide appropriate materials for teaching reading skills. Libraries should be provided for our primary schools, since the absence of libraries is a factor in the deficiency in reading skills. It helped me a lot on finding solutions for many problems that I will face in future in my life as a teacher to help my pupils to reach the successes in their life as students. I learned how to read a lot and how to use the linguistics theories to help my pupils and to learn and discover the problems. The use of miscue analysis is a very useful way to solve pupils weaknesses in communication, because it allows me to focus on the problem itself, and how to deal with each problem individually.

Due to the limited time of this study and the lack of studies that focus on ESL students in public schools, there are a number of important issues that need to be taken into account for future studies. First, it is important to find out whether larger or more diverse populations can lead to the same results. For example, this study focused on two students, but other studies may include different regions with larger populations. This study also focused on two male students; future studies could include females or both genders to explore whether females have different views and challenges than males. Another study could look at perceptions of pre-service teachers who receive education about ESL students. A study like this could provide evidence as to whether teacher education can help teachers to better work with. Families are very important in the learning process to help their children get a better education. Based on the findings of this study, it seems that there was not much communication between families and the mainstream teachers. This lack of communication needs to be taken into account, and some ways to establish good relationships with these families needs to be found. The literature indicates that language and/or culture can be barriers that may prevent these families from coming to school and participating in school activities. However, it is also clear that inviting families to share their language and culture in a particular activity in the classroom may encourage them to participate. Overall communicating with families may help teachers to provide support to ESL students.

Let us now turn our attention to analyzing what we saw. On the left, we can list our observations, and on the right, we can list the principles we derive from our observations.

1. The teacher greets the students, Building a relationship with and introduces himself, and has the among students is very important, students introduce themselves.
2. The teacher accepts what each student says.

Any new learning experience can be threatening. When students have an idea of what will happen in each activity, they often feel more secure. People learn non- defensively when they feel secure.

3. Language is for communication.

The superior knowledge and power of the teacher can be threatening.

If the teacher does not remain in the front of the classroom, the threat is reduced and the students' learning is facilitated. Also this fosters interaction among students, rather than from student to teacher.

1. The teacher should be sensitive to students' level of confidence and give them just what they need to be successful.

Students feel more secure when they know the limits of an activity.

2. Teacher and students are whole persons. Sharing about their learning experience allows learners to get to know one another and to build community.
3. Guided by the knowledge that each learner is unique, the teacher creates an accepting atmosphere. Learners feel free to lower their defenses and the learning experience becomes less threatening.

English language learners, who use at least two languages for processing, struggle with developing English speaking skills. They have culturally different schemata and limited English vocabulary knowledge. Relying on only the first language and using the bottom-up approach exclusively prevent them from improving in speaking. It is important for their teachers to understand them from the cultural, linguistic, and social perspectives and to respect their individual differences. Advocating bi-literacy and using explicit instruction in meaningful contexts are also recommended.

These suggestions aid oral competence of second language learners not only in speaking classes, but also across the content areas where speaking is the fundamental tool for understanding the subject matter.

The list of used literature

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